

Learning Process of Reciting Al-Quran through Short Surah Memorization for Elementary School Studets

Iswan

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: August 22, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: March 23 , 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Learning Process, Reading The Koran, Memorizing Short Surah</p> <hr/> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6378087</p>	<p><i>Research with the title: learning process of reciting al-Quran through short surah memorization for elementary school students. The purpose of this study was to determine the process of reading the Koran through memorizing short surahs for elementary school students. This research was conducted at Muhammadiyah 12 Pamulang Elementary School South Tangerang Indonesia. The research method used is a quantitative descriptive approach. The results showed that memorizing the Koran by grade 3 students was required to memorize short chapters of the Koran such as surah al-Bayyinah, al-Qodr, al-Alaq, at-Tiin, al-Insyirah, ad-Dhuha, al-Lail repeatedly until the students are really fluent in reading. At the time of the implementation of learning to read the al-Quran through memorizing short surahs in class, students are required to repeat the memorization that has been previously memorized together with the aim of memorizing that what has been memorized is still remembered and fluent when students read, according to science, tajwid is makhraj al-letter (place of entry and exit), ahkam al-huruf (relationship between letters), ahkam al-maddi wa al-Qasr (problems of long and short speech), ahkam al-Waaf wa al-Ibtida or problems starting and stop reading the results are very good.</i></p>

Introduction

In today's era of increasingly rapid globalization, in line with the development of the times, there is an urgent need for talents with strength, competitiveness, faith, and loyalty to Allah. Through learning to read the al-Qur'an is the main worship for Muslims which should be done before other acts of worship. Reflecting on the first revelation that came down to the Messenger of Allah, Allah invites and encourages people to seek and explore knowledge, with the words "iqra" which means read. (QS. al-Alaq (96):1-5). In the initial verses there are the words "qalam" which is usually a symbol of knowledge.

Al-Qur'an is a holy book for Muslims, which was revealed to the Prophet Muhammad, through Jibril by rote. Likewise the Prophet Muhammad taught the al-Qur'an to his companions not by writing but by rote. The al-Qur'an is the only holy book whose purity is guaranteed by Allah until the end of time and does not undergo changes, additions, or subtractions. Not a single letter has shifted or changed from its place, and there is not a single letter or word that might be inserted in it, as for in Surah Al-An'am verse 115 Allah says:

وَتَمَّتْ كَلِمَتُ رَبِّكَ صِدْقًا وَعَدْلًا ۚ لَا مُبَدِّلَ لِكَلِمَاتِهِ ۚ وَهُوَ السَّمِيعُ الْعَلِيمُ

Meanings: "The Word of your Lord was fulfilled with truth and justice. Nothing can change His Words. He's the Hearer, the Knower." (QS. Al-An'am: 115)

The al-Qur'an is used as the main source in Islamic education which contains values that have been determined by Allah SWT. The values contained in the al-Qur'an are guidelines that cover all aspects of life that are universal, including aspects of education. In addition, the al-Qur'an since it was first revealed until now, has always maintained its purity, as the word of Allah SWT in QS. Al-Hijr verse 9 that says:

إِنَّا نَحْنُ نَزَّلْنَا الذِّكْرَ وَإِنَّا لَهُ لَحَافِظُونَ

Meanings: *Indeed We have sent down the Reminder, I and indeed We will preserve it. (QS. Al-Hijr:9)*

This verse guarantees the purity of the al-Qur'an forever. Allah's protection of the al-Qur'an does not mean that Allah directly keeps the writing phases of the al-Qur'an, but that Allah involves His servants to participate in guarding the Qur'an. One of the evident efforts in the process of preserving the al-Qur'an is to memorize it in every generation.

Memorizing the al-Qur'an is one of the efforts to maintain the purity of the al-Qur'an. Therefore, lucky are those who can keep the al-Qur'an by memorizing, understanding, and practicing its contents. With the al-Qur'an, Allah elevates the rank of those who memorize the al-Qur'an and wears their parents a crown, whose light is brighter than the sun. Children must often have a dialogue with their parents to ensure the importance of the al-Qur'an both in this world or in the hereafter and the superiority of those who read the al-Qur'an over those who do not read it.

According to Qomariah and Irsyad (2016:11), memorizing the Qur'an is not just worship, but has many benefits, including: a. The al-Qur'an contains about 77,439 sentences. If the memorizers of the Qur'an understand the entire contents of the sentence, it means that they have memorized a lot of Arabic vocabulary; b. In the al-Qur'an there are many words of wisdom that are very valuable for life. Thus by memorizing the al-Qur'an we know many words of wisdom; c. In the al-Qur'an there are many uslub or (expressions) that are very beautiful; d. Memorizing the al-Qur'an allows people to speak fluently and correctly, and can help them in issuing the arguments of the verses of the al-Qur'an quickly when explaining or discussing a problem; e. Strengthens reasoning and memory. People who are accustomed to memorizing the al-Qur'an find it easier to memorize things other than the al-Qur'an.

In practice, it is the duty and obligation of Muslims to preserve and maintain it, one of which is by memorizing it. Al-Qur'an for Muslims has a crucial role and use in everyday life, one of which is as a source of knowledge and intercession for readers and memorizers. Al-Qur'an education must be taught from an early age. The children must be persuaded to love the al-Qur'an through learning al-Qur'an. Teaching the al-Qur'an to children can help develop their thinking in studying the al-Qur'an, if you teach them continuously it will increase children's understanding of the al-Qur'an by memorizing it. Applying learning to read the al-Qur'an through memorization in children can be done by recognizing the hijaiyah letters, their shapes, and ways of reading them and listening to how to pronounce them correctly so that they can help children fluently memorize the al-Qur'an. Memorizing the al-Qur'an is certainly not easy, not only by reading once and immediately memorized but there are methods and problems.

In this era, there are many influences of increasingly rapid technological developments that have positive and negative impacts, especially for children, of course, they are negatively affected by technological developments. Currently, children are addicted to playing games and many playing facilities cause children not to be interested in learning to read the al-Qur'an or memorize it. Parents and teachers are required to have a caring and concerned attitude towards the current condition of children who are the next generation. Therefore we need a place or place to move and motivate and foster children's interest in learning the al-Qur'an by rote. One of the formal institutions is the school.

Problem Statement

1. How to learn to read the Koran through memorizing short surahs at Muhammadiyah 12 Pamulang Elementary School South Tangerang City Indonesia?

2. What method is used in memorizing the al-Qur'an at Muhammadiyah 12 Pamulang Elementary School South Tangerang City Indonesia?

3. What factors support and hinder learning to read the al-Qur'an through memorizing short suras at Muhammadiyah 12 Pamulang Elementary School South Tangerang City Indonesia?

Literature Review

The definition of learning, learning occurs when a stimulus situation along with the contents of memory affects the student so that his actions change from time to time before he experiences the situation to time after he experiences the situation. Learning is an activity or a process to acquire knowledge, improve skills, improve behavior, attitudes and strengthen personality. According to Morgan in Thobroni (2015:18), learning is any relatively permanent change in behavior that occurs as a result of practice or experience. Meanwhile, according to Gagne in Thobroni (2015:18), in Aritonang (2008:3), learning is a relatively permanent change in the potential for action, which takes place as a result of reinforced training.

Furthermore, according to Winkel in Aritonang (2008:3), learning is a mental or psychic activity, which takes place in active interaction with the environment that produces changes in knowledge, understanding, skills, values, and attitudes. According to Slameto (2010:2), learning is a business process carried out by a person to obtain a new change in behavior as a whole, as a result of his own experience in interaction with his environment. Based on some of the theories above, it can be concluded that learning is an activity that acquires one's knowledge and processes in changing behavior.

Reading

According to Sujanto in Siswanti (2012:4), reading is a process carried out and used by readers to get the message to be conveyed through the medium of words or written language. According to Zuchdi in Rahmawati (2017:4), reading is a process of obtaining meaning from printed matter, directly, connecting the visual markers of writing with its meaning. Then indirectly, it means identifying the sound in the word and connecting the meaning. Reading is to get messages from reading. And reading is an activity that is delivered in writing and gets meaning.

Al-Qur'an

According to Darajat (2016:19), the Koran is the word of God in the form of revelations conveyed by Gabriel to the Prophet Muhammad, in which it contains basic teachings that can be developed for all aspects of life through *ijtihad*. The teachings contained in the al-Qur'an consist of two major principles, namely those relating to matters of faith called *aqidah*, and those relating to a charity called *sharia*. In the al-Qur'an, many teachings contain principles relating to activities or efforts to learn through educational institutions and others.

According to Rudiyanto (2014:7), the al-Qur'an in language means reading or being read. Whereas in terms the al-Qur'an is the revelation of Allah SWT was revealed to the prophet Muhammad through Jibril as a guide for mankind. The al-Qur'an was revealed to be a guide for those who want to achieve happiness in this world and the hereafter. The al-Qur'an uses Arabic and is a miracle for the apostle. Most of the verses of the al-Qur'an were revealed in the cities of Mecca and Medina. The contents contained in the al-Qur'an are 6236 verses, 114 chapters, and 30 juz.

Meanwhile, according to Sa'adah and Abas (2016:2), the al-Qur'an is the holy book of Muslims as well as the great message of Allah SWT for all mankind. The al-Qur'an is the word of Allah revealed to His Messenger, the closing of the Prophet, namely the Prophet Muhammad, which begins with Surah Al-Fatihah and ends with Surah An-Naas. The al-Qur'an was revealed by Allah SWT to the Prophet Muhammad through Jibril for 23 years as a guide and light that can bring people out of ignorance, towards the light of guidance and contains Allah's warnings, as well as the straight path. The al-Qur'an is like the spirit in the human body and is the essence of a particle. Furthermore, according to the language in Djalal (2011:4), the word al-Qur'an is *masdar* which means the word *qira'ah* (reading). The al-Qur'an with the meaning of *qira'ah*, as used in verses 17 and 18 of Surah Al-Qiyamah:

إِنَّ عَلَيْنَا جَمْعَهُ وَقُرْءَانَهُ فَإِذَا قَرَأْتَهُ فَاتَّبِعْ قُرْءَانَهُ
(سورة القيامة: 17- 75 - 18)

Artinya: "Indeed it is up to us to put it together and to recite it. And when we have recited it, follow its recitation."

According to Djalal (2011:7), said that the al-Qur'an is derived from the word *qaraa'in* which means that some of the evidence taken from the al-Qur'an is *isim murtajal*, meaning that it was used from the beginning as from the word of Allah, which is *mu'jiz* which was revealed to the Prophet Muhammad, it is clear that these opinions do not have strong reasons and are far from the rules of *isytiqaq*, and are far from the prevailing language understandings. That the al-Qur'an is the word of God in the form of revelation conveyed by Jibril to the Prophet Muhammad and in it contains the main teachings that can be developed as well as a guide for mankind and the al-Qur'an was revealed to be a guide for those who want to achieve happiness in this world and the hereafter.

Hijaiyah Letter

According to Handayani (2013:6), Hijaiyah letters are the original letters of the Arabs. From Ali bin Hasan bin Ali bin Fadhal from his father from Imam Rida as, he said: "Indeed, the first thing that Allah created so that His creatures would know Himself was the writing of the hijaiyah letters, because if someone were to be hit on the head, by a stick because it is considered not fluent in speaking, then the law is that he should be explained about the hijaiyah letters and then given as much *diyath* as he cannot understand.

According to Rusyd (2015:38), Hijaiyah letters are the Arabic alphabet or script. The Arabic script is used in the al-Qur'an and other Arabic writings. There are 29 Hijaiyah letters, namely *Alif, ba, ta, tsa, jim, ha', kho, dal, dzal, ro', za, sin, syin, shod, dhodh, tho, zho, 'ain, ghoin, fa, qof, kaf, lam, mim, nun, wawu, ha, hamzah, ya*. Accordings to Ath Tabari in Siswanti (2012:4), Hijaiyah letters are one of the typical types of language that are displayed in the al-Qur'an. The al-Qur'an is indeed compiled using hijaiyah letters with a different *makhraj* and at the same time implies that the al-Qur'an was revealed in Arabic. Meanwhile, according to Abdurahman and Syuja'bn (2014:1) hijaiyah letters are the letters contained in the al-Qur'an, there are 30 letters. Meanwhile, according to Otory Surasman in Siswanti (2012:4), the hijaiyah letter is the basic key to being able to read the al-Qur'an. Hijaiyah letters are used as spelling to write words or sentences in the al-Qur'an.

Based on the theory of the experts above, it can be concluded that the hijaiyah letters are the Arabic alphabet or script in the al-Qur'an, the 29 hijaiyah letters are *alif, ba, ta, tsa, jim, ha', kho, dal, dzal, ro, za, sin, syin, syod, dhod, tho, zho, 'ain, ghoin, fa, qof, kaf, lam, mim, nun, wawu, ha, hamzah, ya*. Hijaiyah letters are the basic key to being able to read the al-Qur'an and are used as spelling to write words or sentences of the al-Qur'an.

The Ability to Read Al-Qur'an

According to Rauf in Astuti (2013:3), the ability to read the al-Qur'an is an important thing in the child's learning process, because this is a basic ability that must be possessed by children. The ability to read the al-Qur'an should be owned by children from an early age. The ability to read the al-Qur'an is a provision for

children's lives. According to Annuri in Astuti (2013:2), the ability to read the al-Qur'an is the skill to read the al-Qur'an properly and correctly by the guidance of the Shari'ah as explained by the science of tajwid.

Meanwhile, according to Sarikin (2012:5), in assessing students who are able or not able to read the al-Qur'an, it is necessary to group them into several groups according to the ability of students to read the al-Qur'an. The types are as follows: a. The ability to read fluently and correctly, according to Mujawir in Sarikin (2012:5), the word *tartil* comes from the words *Rattalla, Yuratilu, Tartilan* which means to read slowly and pay attention to the recitation; b. Ability to read the al-Qur'an with tajwid and makhraj. Tajwid is how to pronounce letters that stand-alone, letters that are strung together with other letters, train the tongue to remove letters from the *makraj*, pronounce long and short sounds, how to eliminate letter sounds by combining them with letters that follow, heavy or light, hiss, or not and learn stop signs in reading.

Lafadz Tajwid according to language in Rudiyanto (2014:8) means to improve. Meanwhile, according to the term "removing each letter from its place of exit by giving its rights and mustahak", what is meant by letter rights is the original nature that is always together with the letter, such as Al Jahr, Isti'la, istifal, and so on. What is meant by mustahak letters are characteristics that appear from time to time, such as tafkhim, tarqiq, ikhfa, and so on. Accordings to Thoyib and Abidah (2013:7). Tajwid is the study of how to read well. This knowledge is shown in the recitation of the al-Qur'an. The pronunciation of hija'iyah letters must be correct because improper pronunciation does not produce different meanings. The science of recitation aims to guide how to pronounce the verse correctly so that its pronunciation and meaning are preserved. The problems covered in tajwid are *makhraj al-huruf* (place of entry and exit), *ahkam al-huruf* (relationships between letters), *ahkam al-maddi waal-qasr* (problems of long and short speech), *ahkam al-waaf waal-ibtida* (problems of starting and stopping reading), and *al-katt al-Ustmani* (problems of the writing of the Ottoman manuscripts).

According to Rudiyanto (2014:8), the law of studying tajwid, in theory, is fardhu kifayah, while the law of reading the al-Qur'an under the rules of tajwid is fardhu'ain. Furthermore, according to Rusyd (2015:34), linguistically, tajwid (تجوید) comes from the word jawwadayujawwidutajwiidan (تجويدا-يجود-جود) which means to refine, improve, or perfect. Meanwhile, according to the term, recitation of knowledge that is useful for improving the reading of the al-Qur'an following these rules includes pronouncing the letters of the al-Qur'an according to their original characteristics, thick or thin, long or short, and various other rules related to the science of recitation. According to Sudiarjo et al., (2015:2), the obligation to read the al-Qur'an with Tajwid is as follow:

Evidences from the al-Qur'an

The Word of Allah Azzawa Jalla

أَوْزُدْ عَلَيْهِ وَرَتَّلِ الْقُرْآنَ تَرْتِيلاً

Meanings: "or add to it, and recite the Qur'an in a measured tone." (Al-Muzzamil4).

The Word of Allah Azzawa Jalla

الَّذِينَ اتَّيْنَاهُمْ الْكِتَابَ يَتْلُونَهُ حَقَّ تِلَاوَتِهِ أُولَئِكَ يُؤْمِنُونَ بِهِ وَمَنْ يَكْفُرْ بِهِ فَأُولَئِكَ هُمُ الْخَاسِرُونَ

Meanings: "Those to whom we have given the Book follow it as it ought to be followed: they have faith in it. As for those who defy it is they who are the losers." (Al-Baqarah:121).

They don't actually read except with tajwid, if they leave it, the reading becomes the worst reading and sometimes it can change the meaning. This verse shows the praise of Allah Almighty for those who read the al-Qur'an with the actual reading.

a. Izhar

Izhar in language means clear, in the science of Tajwid, what is meant by izhar is reading where the sound of nun when nun dies or tanwin meets the letters of izhar is read clearly.

The letters of Izhar are (ا ح خ ع غ ه)

b. Idgham

Idgham is entering or changing the sound of the letter nun when nun mati or tanwin meets idgham letters to idgham letters. Each idgham reading is two harakat.

The letters: mim (م), nun (ن), wau (و), ya' (ي), ro (ر), dan lam (ل)

1. Ikhfa

Ikhfa is hiding or vague, which means to hide or disguise the sound of the letter nun when nun mati or tanwin meets the letters ikhfa. All reading with ikhfa is two harakat.

The letters of Ikhfa are ت ث ج د ذ س ش ص ض ط ظ ف ق ك

2. Qalqalah

Qalqalah is reading the sounds of the letters of qalqalah by bouncing because they are marked with sukun or waqaf. The letters of qalqalah are summarized in sentences "baju di thoqo". The letters ق , ط , ب , ج , د

3. Iqlab

The law of iqlab occurs when nun mati or tanwin meets the letter "ba", where the sound of the letter nun when nun mati or tanwin meets the letter "ba" is read as mim accompanied by buzzing. Every reading that contains iqlab is read two harakat. The Iqlab letter is (ب)

4. Mad

Mad means lengthening the sound of the letters. In tajwid lessons there are two kinds of mad, namely mad ashli or tabi'i and mad far'i ashli which mean principal and far'i means branch.

The law of mastering the science of tajwidi is fard kifayah. This means that if there are Muslims who learn or master the science of tajwid, then our obligations fall. Although learning and mastering the science of tajwid is kifayah, reading the al-Qur'an correctly (according to the rules of tajwid) is obligatory. On that basis, studying and mastering the science of tajwid is obligatory so that our reading of the al-Qur'an is not wrong.

According to Rusyd (2015:36), in studying the science of tajwid there are benefits from studying it, being loved by Allah, and getting a reward from Him, our reading of the al-Qur'an becomes perfect, both in terms of pronunciation of letters, characteristics of letters, tajwid rules and so on, therefore we avoid fatal mistakes or not, besides that it makes it easier for us to understand the meaning of words and sentences in the verses we read. What is meant by makhraj is the place where the hijaiyah letters come out. So the ability of makhraj is the ability to say the hijaiyah letters that match their exact output.

According to H. Subhan Nur in Sudiarjo, et al (2015:2), makharijul letters are the places where letters come out or where letters are pronounced. Broadly speaking, makharijul letters are divided into 5, jauf (oral cavity), halqi (throat cavity), orali (tongue), syafatani (two lips), and khaisyum (nose). Makharijul is place where the sound of the hijaiyah letter comes out when it is read so that the sound of the letter can be distinguished from the sound of other letters. Makharijul letters are divided into 5 parts:

a. Syafatani

Syafatani is a makhraj letter which is located on the two upper and lower lips. The letters are فوهم

1). Lisan

Lisan is the makhraj of letters located on the tongue. The tip of the tongue with the tip of the upper teeth the letter are ظنذ

2). Tongue with upper tooth, the letters دنط

3). The tip of the tongue with the upper dentition. The dentition is a swelling over the top of the upper dentition. The letters are صسنز

4). Between the tip of the tongue and the head of the tongue that is slightly in front of the upper dentition. The head of the tongue is before the tip of the tongue. The letter is ن

5). Near the letter makhraj ن and a little deeper is letter ر

6). Tongue head with upper teeth veins is letter ل

7). Middle tongue with palate, the letters جشي

8). Slightly in front of the base of the tongue with the roof of the mouth, the letter is ك

9). The base of the tongue with the roof of the mouth, the letter is ق

10). The edge of the base of the tongue with the left or right molars extending to the front, the letter is ض

b. Halq

Halq is the letter makhraj located in the throat, those are:

1) Upper throat tip, the letters are غخ

2) Mid throat, the letters are حع

3) Lower larynx, the letters are هـهـ

c. Jauf

Jauf is a makhraj located in the oral cavity, the letters Mad when it serves as a long reading sign, those are:

1) Before Alif there is Fathah ا

2) Before silent Ya there is Kasrah ي

3) Before silent Wa there is Dhamah و

4) Khaisyum

Al-khaisyum is the letter makhraj located at the bridge of the nose, which is all the buzzing sound, for example nun or mim tasjid. The ability to read the al-Qur'an is important in the child's learning process and the ability to read the al-Qur'an is the basis that children must have from an early age.

Tahfidz Al-Qur'an

According to Cahyani and Saidah (2016:4) Tahfidz comes from Arabic which means to memorize, while the word "memorizing" comes from the word "memorize" which has two meanings: it has entered the memory (about the lesson) and may say it out of the head (without looking at it). Books or other notes, the meaning of memorizing is trying to absorb it into the mind so that we always remember. According to Sa'adah and Abas (2016:4) Memorizing the al-Qur'an is a task and great responsibility, everyone can certainly memorize it but not everyone can memorize the al-Qur'an well. The problems faced by people who are memorizing the al-Qur'an are

many and varied. Starting from the development of interest the creation of the environment, the division of time, to the memorization method itself.

According to Sugiati (2016:9), memorizing the al-Qur'an is a noble job, but memorizing the al-Qur'an is not as easy as turning the palm, therefore there are things that need to be prepared before memorizing so that the memorization process is not so heavy. The requirements for memorizing the al-Qur'an are according to Nurkhozin and Nurcholis (2016:173), first is a strong intention, second is consistent, third is guided by a tahfidz teacher, and fourth is to leave immorality.

According to Rusyd (2015:165), in memorizing the al-Qur'an, of course, there are instructions for memorizing the al-Qur'an, the first is a strong intention, the second has a strong will and patience, the third is consistency or *istiqamah*, the fourth is to decorate yourself with commendable character, and the fifth is to use one manuscript. That memorization comes from Arabic is *tahfidz*. Memorizing the al-Qur'an is a noble job and has a large responsibility and in memorizing the al-Qur'an one must have a strong intention, strong ability, patience, and consistency.

The Importance of Memorizing the al-Qur'an

According to Qomariah and Irsyad (2016:1), memorizing the al-Qur'an is a noble act, both in front of humans and in front of Allah SWT. Many virtues are obtained by memorizing the al-Qur'an, both in the world and in the hereafter. The virtues of memorizing the al-Qur'an are as follows: a. Having a high position with Allah, Allah gives a high and honorable position to the memorizers of the al-Qur'an among other humans; b. Opportunity to become a leader, People who memorize the Koran are the most entitled to lead. This is as the words of the Prophet Muhammad entered into the high class of human beings; c. Memorizing the al-Qur'an is classified as the highest human being in heaven, depending on the amount of memorization he has; d. Made as a family of Allah SWT. The memorizers of the al-Qur'an are referred to as the family of Allah; e. Will get intercession on the Day of Judgment later the Koran will come to intercede for readers and memorizers so that memorizing the Koran can be a provision in the hereafter; f. Beings a helper for their parents, the memorizers of the Koran in the last days can put a crown on their parents; g. The best of people, people who memorize the Koran (including those who study the Koran) are among those who get the title of the best people; h. Always shaded by Allah's mercy, Those who memorize the al-Qur'an will get love from Allah, serenity, surrounded by angels, and praised by Allah in front of His other creatures; i. Angels will always accompany, In the hereafter people who memorize the Koran will be gathered with the angels; j. Getting a lot of good, the memorizers of the Koran have a lot of goodness from the Koran that he reads. The virtue of memorizing the al-Qur'an can be with Allah and get a lot of goodness.

Benefits of Memorizing the Quran

According to Umarulfaruq Abubakar in Qomariah and Irsyad (2016:11), memorizing the Koran is not just worship, but has many benefits, both physically and psychologically. This is evidenced by a study in Riyadh whose results concluded that memorizing the Koran can increase the body's immunity. According to Sugianto in Qomariah and Irsyad (2016:11), there are several benefits of memorizing the Koran: a. Al-Quran contains about 77,439 sentences. If the memorizer of the Koran understands the entire contents of the sentence, it means that he has memorized a lot of Arabic vocabulary; b. In the al-Qur'an, there are many words of wisdom that are very valuable for life. Thus, by memorizing the Koran he knows many words of wisdom; c. In the al-Qur'an, there are many *uslub* (idioms) or *ta'bir* (expressions) that are very beautiful. For someone who wants to get a fluent "dza'iq arabi" (literary image) to later become an Arabic writer, it is necessary to memorize many beautiful Arabic words, and they are already contained in the Koran; d. Memorization of reading the al-Qur'an allows people to speak fluently and correctly and can help them in issuing the arguments of the verses of the al-Qur'an quickly when explaining or discussing a problem; e. Strengthens reasoning and memory. People who are used to memorizing the Koran easily memorize things other than the Koran. Many children who memorize the Koran have a higher level of progress in learning compared to other friends who do not memorize the Koran.

There are many benefits of memorizing the al-Qur'an. One of them is that it can strengthen memory and make people who memorize the al-Qur'an fluent in speaking Arabic.

Methods and Strategies for Memorizing the Quran

A method is one of the important things in educating children to memorize the al-Qur'an, especially elementary school children. Many methods might be developed to find alternatives to educate children to memorize the al-Qur'an. According to Ahsin W. Al-Hafiz in Qomariah and Irsyad (2016:41), there are several methods in teaching children to memorize the Koran:

1. Wahdah Method

The wahdah method is that the child memorizes the memorized verses one by one. In the early stages, each verse can be read ten times or twenty times or more, so that this process can form a pattern in its image. Thus, the child can condition the verses he has memorized, not only in his imagination but to form his verbal reflexes. After memorizing, then proceed to the next verse with the same model.

2. Kitabah Method.

This method provides an alternative to the wahdah method. In this method, parents write on a piece of paper the verses that the child has memorized. Some verses are memorized by the child, depending on the child's ability. Parents can measure the written verses with their child's ability to memorize.

3.Sima'I Method (Listening).

The sima'i method is listening to the reading of the verses of the al-Qur'an which are memorized by the child. This method is very effective for children who have a high memory, especially for children who have not been able to read the Koran. This method can be done with two alternatives: (a). Children hear readings from parents directly. In this case, parents are required to play a more active, patient, and thorough role in reading verses and guiding children in memorizing. Parents read the verse one by one then the child repeats the verse until he can memorize it fluently; (b). Parents first record the verses that are memorized by the child according to the child's ability. Then the recording is played and played to the child repeatedly until the child memorizes it.

4. Combined Method.

This method is a combination of the Wahdah method and the Kitabah method. It's just that Kitabah (writing) has a function as a test for the verses he has memorized. The sequence, after memorizing, the children were told to write down the verses that had been memorized. Meanwhile, according to Abidin (2016:11), there are several methods that can be used in memorizing short surahs: (1) Maudhawi Ma'arif Method. This method has three principles. *First*, preparation This preparation requires the memorizers of Juz 'Amma to memorize one letter every day correctly and correctly, and choose the right time to memorize. *Second* validation or deposit, after making the best possible preparation, and remembering the surah, the next step is to "deposit" the memorization to the supervising teacher. Supervising teachers are very important so that our memorization process can be more easily and quickly corrected. *Third*, repetition, repetition (*muraja'ah* or guarding) is done after depositing the memorization to the supervisor. After depositing, it is not allowed to leave the class (*majlis tahfizh*) before the memorization deposited is repeated several times. (2) Talaqqi Method. The talaqqi method comes from the sentence *laqia* which means to meet, what is meant to meet here is the meeting between students and teachers. The talaqqi method is to deposit or listen to the memorization that has just been memorized by a teacher. Judging from the teaching system, this *talaqqi* method consists of two parts. First, a teacher reads or conveys his knowledge in front of his students. While the students listened to it and ended with a question. Second, students read in front of the teacher, then the teacher confirms if there are errors in the student's reading. (3) Takrir Method. The method of memorizing the al-Qur'an, especially Juz 'Amma, the meaning of takrir is repeating memorization or memorizing what has been memorized. Takrir is intended so that the memorization that has been memorized is maintained properly. In addition to the teacher, takrir can also be done alone to launch memorization that has been memorized so that it is not easy to forget.

Based on the opinion of the experts above method is one of the important things in educating children to memorize the al-Qur'an and many methods can be used in memorizing the al-Qur'an such as the Wahdah method, the Kitabah method, the Sima'i method, combined method, and so on.

Strategies to Educate Memorizing the al-Qur'an

The strategy of educating children to memorize the al-Qur'an from an early age is usually interpreted as a plan determined by parents in educating children so that they can memorize the Koran from an early age through various appropriate actions and supported by existing resources. According to Qomariah and Irsyad (2016:16), the strategies that can be done by parents in educating children to memorize the Koran from an early age are as follows: a. Starting from the grand vision of parents, vision is a foresight, which is desired to be achieved in a certain time and with a certain effort, about a dream and high ideals. The existence of a great vision in a person's life will make him more able to appreciate life, because he has a clear purpose in life, including the vision of having a child who is a hafiz and a hafizah who memorizes the Koran; b. Instilling a love for the Koran in children, instilling a love for the Koran in children is an important thing that must be done by parents if they want their children to become memorizers of the Koran. Because if a child loves the Koran then they have received the love of Allah and the messenger of Allah. This is as explained by the Prophet in the following words:

مَنْ أَحَبَّ أَنْ يُجِبَّهَ اللَّهُ وَرَسُولُهُ فَلْيَنْظُرْ، فَإِنْ كَانَ يُحِبُّ الْقُرْآنَ فَهُوَ يُحِبُّ اللَّهَ وَرَسُولَهُ

Artinya: "Whoever wants to be loved by Allah and His Messenger should pay attention to this: if he loves the al-Qur'an, it means that he loves Allah and His Messenger." (HR. Thabrani)

Supporting factors for educating children to memorize the al-Qur'an

Educating children to memorize the al-Qur'an from an early age, of course, cannot be separated from several factors, both supporting factors, and inhibiting factors. Everyone has different supporting and inhibiting factors in doing something. Likewise the efforts the Abu Hilyah family in educating their children to memorize the al-Qur'an from an early age in Qomariah and Erysyad (2016:134). Based on the results of interviews and observations, it is known that Abu Hilyah and his wife in educating children to memorize the al-Qur'an from an early age are: a. The are background of the parents, the success or failure of the child is also influenced by the educational background of the parents. Because the education they get will affect the way they educate their children; b. Exemplary parents, Teaching the Koran must be exemplified for children that the al-Qur'an must be a part of life and good morals must be prioritized in supporting children to memorize the Koran from an early age; c. The role of recitation institutions in educating children memorize the al-Qur'an recitation institutions also play a role; d. The use of media, in any case, the media is always a supporting factor if used properly, including in educating children to memorize the al-Qur'an from an early age.

Inhibiting Factors in Educating Children to Memorizing the al-Qur'an

In addition to supporting factors in educating children to memorize the al-Qur'an, some factors prevent children from memorizing the al-Qur'an. According to Abidin (2016:69), there are inhibiting factors in educating children to memorize the al-Qur'an such as: a. Feeling lazy, impatient, and hopeless is a barrier to memorization. Laziness is a common and frequent mistake in studying, working, and worshipping, and also memorizing Juz 'Amma or short surahs; b. It is difficult to manage time. In a day there are 24 hours, this number applies to everyone, whether or not everyone is willing to live it in everything, especially memorizing Juz 'Amma, these hours must be optimized. Prospective memorizers are required to be smarter in using time, both for world affairs and memorizing tasks; c. Forgetfulness, in memorizing the al-Qur'an, forgetting is divided into two, human or natural forgetting and forgetting due to negligence. Natural forgetting is not remembering which is usually experienced when the memorization proceeds to become rote. While forgetting because of negligence comes from the memorizers themselves. In essence, he did not forget, except because he did not want to read his memorization again, according to the frequency of his reading; d. Rarely Repeating, when memorizing, we find it difficult to record the verses that are being memorized it is a small problem. Knowing the frequency of time and repetition of the verses is still very little.

Research Finding

Data Analysis Results

Based on the observations of researchers in the field, grade 3 students are very active and happy. Researchers made observations during tahfidz learning activities. When tahfidz learning activities make students excited in memorizing the Koran or short surahs so researchers are interested in conducting research. Then the time shows at 7 o'clock when students enter the classroom. Then students start learning by praying together first using English and Indonesian. After that, the tahfidz teacher asked the students to take out the tahfidz book and Juz 'Amma, the students were asked to repeat or read short surahs that had been memorized together. In this learning process, the tahfidz teacher uses the takrir method, namely repeating memorization the intended takrir is so that the memorization of students who have been memorized is maintained properly. The students were so excited to read the verses of the short surah while looking at Juz 'Amma.

After completing the memorization, the teacher asked the students to memorize Surah Al-Alaq and the students began to memorize Surah Al-Alaq. Before memorizing the tahfidz teacher gave an example of reading and taught the students to use the *wahdah* method, the child memorized one by one the verses to be memorized. Each verse can be read five to ten times, so this process can form a pattern in its image. In addition, the tahfidz teacher uses the *Sima'i* (listening) method, namely listening to the reading of verses of the al-Qur'an or short suras that will be memorized. So the two methods are combined. At the initial stage, the teacher reads each verse five to ten times, then the students listen to the teacher's reading directly while looking at Juz'Amma and the students repeat the verse until they can memorize fluently and correctly.

After that, students who have memorized are allowed to come forward to give their memorization. Tahfidz teachers use the talaqqi method, where students deposit their memorization and the teacher listens to the memorization that has just been memorized by students. Then the tahfidz teacher justifies if there are errors in the student's reading. Students who have not come forward to do their memorization activities in different ways some students memorize by themselves, some memorize together, some are playing and listening to their friends memorize.

Tahfidz/Teacher Informants Observation

Mrs. YN is a tahfidz teacher in grade 3. To teach tahfidz, she has been teaching for a long time. Mrs. YN is a teacher who is patient with her students, thorough and good at teaching students to memorize short surahs of the Koran. Mrs. YN patiently guides her students one by one in learning to read the al-Qur'an through memorizing short suras. She is a teacher who understands the difficulties of her students. Mrs. YN always looks for solutions to any obstacles or difficulties her students experience in memorizing short surahs of the al-Qur'an.

She never forces every student to memorize quickly. She allows her students to memorize the short surahs of the al-Qur'an according to their abilities. Mrs. YN wants her students to feel comfortable in the learning process. Mrs. YN also always invites students to repeat the memorization that has been memorized at the beginning of the lesson so that it is not easy to forget and always remembers. Students who take tahfidz lessons are 3rd-grade students at Muhammadiyah 12 Pamulang Elementary School, South Tangerang City Indonesia totaling 33 people. However, based on appropriate data for research and through suggestions from tahfidz teachers, there were only ten people.

Tahfidz Teacher Interview Results

One of the subjects of this research is the teacher Tahfidz who is at the Muhammadiyah 12 Pamulang Elementary School South Tangerang City Indonesia. All subjects of this research have taken data in the form of interviews.

How do you introduce hijaiyah letters to grade 3 students at Muhammadiyah 12 Pamulang Elementary School? Mrs. YN said: Hijaiyah letters from grade 1 have been taught, in grade 3 they review it again and make

sure students know all hijaiyah letters. For students who haven't memorized it too well or forgotten, I use cardboard and the hijaiyah letters are pasted, but for grade 3 students, they are able or know the hijaiyah letters.

Based on the results of interviews that have been conducted with Mrs. YN that she has introduced hijaiyah letters to students starting from grade 1 and for grade 3 only by repeating or making sure that students can know all the letters hijaiyah. Then Mrs. YN used cardboard media with hijaiyyah letters on it so that it was easier for students to understand the letters.

Are students able to pronounce hijaiyah letters according to the makhorijul letters? Mrs. YN said: Yes, God willing, they are able to do it. Based on the results of interviews conducted that grade 3 students at Muhammadiyah 12 Pamulang Elementary School have been able to pronounce hijaiyah letters according to the makhorijul letters.

How do you teach students to pronounce hijaiyah letters properly and correctly?

Mrs. YN said: Yes, by giving examples according to the makhorijul letters, then using the video and the sheet of paper containing the video. Then students imitate the video like ba, bi, bu, ba.

Based on the results of interviews that have been conducted, the method used by the tahfidz teacher in teaching students to pronounce the hijaiyah letters properly and correctly is by giving examples of reading according to the makhorijul letters.

In addition, the teacher also uses videos of the pronunciation of the hijaiyah letters in teaching students to pronounce the hijaiyah letters and students are given a paper containing how to pronounce the hijaiyah letters from the video, for example ba, bi, bu, bab in this way it is hoped that students can pronounce the hijaiyah letters well. and correct according to the letters makhorijul.

How to find out the students' ability to read the short surah of the Qur'an?

Mrs. YN said: By calling each child or one by one forward and listening to students memorize the Qur'an or short suras and make reports. Because each child has a different ability to pronounce the letters and the children bring characters from their respective regions.

Based on the results of interviews that have been carried out, to find out the students' ability to read the Qur'an or short suras is to call the students to the front and the students read the Qur'an or short suras and then she made the report.

How do you teach reciting the Qur'an properly and correctly according to the makraj and tajwid?

Mrs. YN said: By giving an example of reciting the al-Qur'an or the surah, then listen to the children whether the pronunciation is correct or not and repeat it until everything is correct. For example, bismillah, if you don't use that tone, I will ask students to stop reading it because it is wrong and the tone also has an effect, as I read the following Bismilahirrahmanirahim because with that tone the reading is correct because it lengthens the short one.

Based on the results of interviews that have been conducted, Mrs. YN has been taught how to read the al-Qur'an properly and correctly according to her makraj and tajwid to grade 3 students. Mrs. YN gives examples of pronunciation to students and listens to students until the student reciting is correct.

Do you use lesson plans in tahfidz learning?

Mrs. YN said: There is no lesson plan yet.

Based on the results of interviews that have been carried out that tahfidz learning at Muhammadiyah 12 Pamulang Elementary School so far, tahfidz learning activities have not used a learning implementation plan because the school does not have a tahfidz learning implementation plan. Therefore, Mrs. YN only teaches based on what she has planned in each lesson. It is hoped that future tahfidz learning will use a learning implementation plan so that the teaching and learning process is more focused and the goals to be achieved are clear.

How do the tahfidz test for students?

Mrs. YN said: By calling students according to the order and assessing students and evaluating how far they have memorized using the Tahfidz book.

Based on the results of interviews that have been conducted, the tahfidz teacher performed a memorization test for students by calling the students in the order, then the students came to the front of the class and read the short memorization of the surah then the teacher listened and assessed and evaluated the memorization using the tahfidz book. It is based on the results of the researcher during observations.

In tahfidz, what short suras do you give to students?

Mrs. YN said: For the third grade from surah Al-Bayyinah, Al-Qodr, Al-Alaq, At-Tiin, Al-Insyirah, Ad-Dhuha, Al-Lail it is the minimum standard. If it's more than that, even better. Based on the results of interviews that have been carried out, the tahfidz learning at Muhammadiyah 12 Pamulang Elementary School has different memorization standards in each class. Grade 3 students are required to memorize Surahs Al-Bayyinah, Al-Qodr, Al-Alaq, At-Tiin, Al-Insyirah, Ad-Dhuha, Al-Lail, which is a minimum standard in grade 3 if students can memorize from other surahs it would be much better.

How many short surahs should students memorize in one meeting?

Mrs. YN said: In one meeting, there are 5 verses for the long surah, and for the short surah it is 1 verse. Based on the results of the interviews that have been conducted, grade 3 students must submit 5 verses for long surah and 1 verse for short surah. Based on the results of observations, grade 3 students always deposit their memorization well. Have the students been able to achieve the target of memorizing the short surahs that you have set?

Mrs. YN said: Yes, they have. Based on the results of interviews that have been conducted, grade 3 students have been able to achieve the target of memorizing short surahs. It is based on the observation that grade 3 students have been able to memorize the specified short surahs or according to the minimum standard, there are even 3rd-grade students who have been able to exceed the specified short surahs.

In your opinion, what is the priority in memorizing the Qur'an?

Mrs. YN said: For children, I want them not only to memorize it but to know the meaning of the surah and apply it in their daily life. Based on the results of interviews that have been conducted that the virtue of memorizing the al-Qur'an is that students not only memorize the al-Qur'an but students must know the meaning and meaning of the surah and be able to apply it in everyday life.

In your opinion, what are the benefits of memorizing the al-Qur'an?

Mrs. YN said: The benefits for children are that they can focus and concentrate on learning, it is easier to remember because they are used to memorizing the al-Qur'an. Moreover, it is held in the morning of the tahfidz so my intention in the morning, the child begins by memorizing the al-Qur'an because it is more focused and fast in remembering. Hopefully, in the next lesson, they will be more enthusiastic and confident with the existing lessons.

Based on the results of interviews that the benefits of memorizing the al-Qur'an are that students can focus and concentrate more on learning. In addition, students are easier to remember quickly.

What method do you use in al-Qur'an short surahs tahfidz?

Mrs. YN said: By using the Wahdah, Takrir (repeating), and Sima'I methods by giving an example once and then repeating it five to ten times. Then the students listened directly to the teacher and the children imitated but looked at the Juz'Amma so that the makhrāj was correct, the length and the recitation were correct. Only after five times did the children close the Juz'Amma or the al-Qur'an and try whether they had memorized it or not. If not, it's okay to open Juz'Amma. In addition, it also uses the talaqqi method, when students give their memorization, I listen to their memorization and assess them.

Based on the results of interviews that have been conducted that the method used by tahfidz teachers at Muhammadiyah 12 Pamulang Elementary School is using the wahdah method, the Sima'I method, the takrir method, and the talaqqi method which are combined into one, the teacher gives an example once and repeats five to ten times, then students listen to the teacher directly and students imitate while looking or reading Juz'Amma. After that, the students closed Juz'Amma and tried it whether they had memorized it or not. If there are students who have not memorized it, they can look at the book again. In this way, students are able to memorize quickly. This is based on the observations of students chanting verses with enthusiasm and confidence and students are able to memorize short surahs quickly.

How is the application of the method of memorizing the al-Qur'an that you use in tahfidz learning?

Mrs. YN said: Same as before by giving an example once, then repeating and repeating five to ten times. Then the children listen to the way I pronounce and imitate it by looking at Juz'Amma so that the makhrāj is correct, the length is short and the tajwid is correct. After five times, the children close the Juz'Amma or the al-Qur'an and try whether they have memorized it or not. If you haven't memorized it, it's fine to open Juz'Amma again.

Based on the results of interviews that have been conducted, the application of the tahfidz learning method in the classroom is by giving an example once and then repeating it five to ten times. Then the students just listen to the teacher directly and imitate while looking at the Juz'Amma so that the makhrāj is correct, the length is short and the recitation is correct. After five repetitions the students close the Juz'Amma or the al-Qur'an and try whether they have memorized it or not. Thus students are able to memorize and in this case, the tahfidz teacher is required to be more active, patient, and thorough in guiding grade 3 students.

How is the memorization system at Muhammadiyah 12 Pamulang Elementary School? Is the limited time sufficient for all students to memorize?

Mrs. YN said: By allowing children who have memorized to give their memorization and if there are children who have not memorized they are immediately called their children. In one day it is one child for 5 to 7 minutes. Alhamdulillah, within one hour of one class the time is sufficient.

Based on the results of interviews that have been carried out, the system of giving memorization in grade 3 Pamulang 12 Elementary School is by allowing students who have memorized to come forward, and those who have not memorized will still be called. In giving memorization for one student, it takes about three to seven minutes and within one hour it is enough for all students to memorize.

How long does it take for each student to give their memorization?

Mrs. YN said: Five to seven minutes but I don't dwell on it. For children who are easy or who have good pronunciation, two to three minutes are done. But for example, more than that time until the child reads it correctly, because when children have memorized the wrong reading, it is difficult to correct it. So, in the beginning, I read it according to the makraj and tajwid.

Based on the results of the interviews that have been conducted, the time required for each student to memorize is three to seven minutes and there is no problem with excess time because Mrs. YN is not based on that time.

What is the strategy that you use in educating students so that students quickly memorize the al-Qur'an (short suras)?

Mrs. YN said: Five to ten times the short recitation of one verse at a time and if the recitation is long like Al-Bayyinah it is cut into three (one verse is cut into three parts) or until waqf. Children already know that it stops there. We memorize it first until the waqf is done then after they see the writing five times they try to close the Juz'Amma and see if they can memorize it or not.

Based on the results of interviews that the strategy used for students to quickly memorize the Koran or short surahs is by repeating five to ten readings and for short verses one verse at a time. For long surahs like surah al-Bayyinah, in one verse it is cut into three parts. In your opinion, is there any effort from the school in providing support and motivating students in tahfidz al-Qur'an (short surah)?

Mrs. YN said: Alhamdulillah, there is a lot of motivation and then support the existence of Tahfidz every morning one hour from 7 to 8 am. So, between one day reading the al-Qur'an or Iqro and the next day Tahfidz. Then every day the children read the Surah with loudspeakers from 6.30 to 7 AM. Each child has a schedule that has been determined by their children who are already good at pronouncing and also the makhraj. The 6th grade is from An-Naba and below 30 minutes from 6.30 to 7 AM with a loudspeaker. So there is a schedule and parents already know that their child has a schedule for reading the al-Qur'an and at 6.30 AM they arrive at school.

Based on the results of interviews that have been conducted that the Muhammadiyah 12 Pamulang Elementary School has provided motivation and support with the existence of tahfidz by providing opportunities for students who have good pronunciation and correct makraj as well as tajwid to read the al-Qur'an every morning from 6.30 until 7 AM. In your opinion, what are the supporting factors in educating students memorize the al-Qur'an through short suras at school?

Mrs. YN said: Many of the supporting factors come from internal, external, and parents. The parents are to murojoah or repeat the memorization at school and ask where the memorization has reached. Then the 3rd graders are given a reward or gift so that the children are enthusiastic. It must be remembered not just to get a gift, but children must feel the benefits of memorizing the al-Qur'an. With such support, it is better and at school, the teacher is as comfortable as possible in learning to memorize the al-Qur'an and does not make it a burden because if it becomes a burden, they will quickly remember but also forget quickly.

Based on the results of interviews that have been conducted that there are supporting factors in memorizing the short surah of the al-Qur'an. Many of these supporting factors come from internal, external, school, and parents. For parents, provide support to students and their memorization students and ask how far they have memorized. Besides that, people know how to give rewards or prizes to students in memorizing the al-Qur'an so that students are enthusiastic about memorizing. In addition, the teacher provides a comfortable attitude to students so that memorizing is more fun and not made a burden. Do you use tahfidz media and guidebooks in the process of tahfidz activities in class?

Mrs. YN said: Yes, this is the tahfidz book, in the tahfidz manual on page 10 there are prayers. Each child memorizes his prayer, then on page 14, there are surahs. In the long surah we have 5 stages, the first stage, for example, a new child can have 5 verses, it's okay to accept it and then proceed to the second stage until the surah or verse is finished. On page 20 there are achievements of Iqra and the al-Qur'an, usually one day for the al-Qur'an is 3 verses so that there is enough time for Iqro 1 sheet.

Based on the results of interviews that have been conducted that learning tahfidz at Muhammadiyah 12 Pamulang Elementary School uses the tahfidz guide book. In the tahfidz book there are prayers that must be memorized by students, then there is the memorization of short surah and the achievements of Iqro and the Qur'an. What are the inhibiting factors for students in memorizing the Qur'an (short surah)?

Mrs. YN said: The atmosphere in the morning is not good for memorizing because they wake up late, so every child who wakes up must be conditioned to be in a good mood. Then the Fajr prayer must be on time, do not oversleep, and have breakfast so that the child is not sleepy or weak, from waking up the child's mood is affected. Then when in class there are friends who have finished memorizing while some have not finished it becomes an obstacle, meaning that they are conditioned for other activities, for example, those who have finished can draw, sit or read books so that children who have not finished memorizing do not want to play or not disturbed. On average, when their friends play, they want to play too. So they are carried away by the situation or the atmosphere of their friends who have finished.

Based on the results of interviews that have been carried out, what is an obstacle for students in memorizing is the mood condition of students which affects memorizing the short surah of the al-Qur'an, besides the condition of students who are still sleepy or weak. Then when a friend who has finished depositing his memorization and there are students who have not finished it becomes an obstacle. Because students who have not finished memorizing want to play with their friends who have finished and as a result they are carried away by the situation so that the atmosphere in the class becomes crowded and many students run around or play

In your opinion, what are the obstacles in educating students to memorize the Qur'an (short suras)?

Mrs. YN said: The actual obstacle is not too much or little, even it is not considered as an obstacle, for example when a child is sick. When his friend's memorization is high and he feels he is not finished. Usually, we motivate or provide support and encouragement for children to remain consistent in memorizing. I do not make it an obstacle but how to find a way or a solution. Every child is different, for example, for children who seem less enthusiastic, they are approached and guided more than others, or for example, in etiquette, I have found children who have not been able to read the al-Qur'an and find it difficult to memorize because they cannot read the verses. I use the method book, which is to write the verse in Latin so that the Latin is written first, the children are more enthusiastic. For example, in class, there is a student like Fatia. Fatia is already Iqro 6 but she's having a hard time keeping it short. So with Latin writing, she is more confident and the obstacles are looked for ways or solutions so they don't become obstacles.

Based on the results of interviews that have been conducted, the factors that hinder teachers in educating students to memorize the al-Qur'an at Muhammadiyah 12 Pamulang Elementary School are few or no obstacles because teachers do not make them obstacles and look for ways or solutions. The results of the study, have obtained the results of research documentation at Muhammadiyah 12 Pamulang Elementary School South Tangerang City in learning tahfidz al-Qur'an short surahs as follows :

Picture 1: Tahfidz learning activities process

The atmosphere when grade 3 students repeat their memorization together. And continued by the teacher teaching to read the short chapters with methods so that children memorize quickly.

Picture2: Learning activities to know reading the al-Qur'an

TA is a grade 3 student at Muhammadiyah 12 Pamulang Elementary School. TA is one of the students who is still reading Iqro 4 but can already memorize the short surahs of the Koran. TA has been able to memorize short suras in grade 3 such as Al-Bayyinah, Al-Qodr, Al-Alaq.

Picture3: Student learning activities to read the al-Qur'an

AH is a grade 3 student at Muhammadiyah 12 Pamulang Elementary School. AH is still reading Iqro 4 and has been able to memorize short surahs of the Koran such as Surah Al-Bayyinah, Al-Qodr, Al-Alaq for a minimum standard in grade 3.

SB is a grade 3 student at Muhammadiyah 12 Pamulang Elementary School. SB is one of the students who are able to read the al-Qur'an. SB has been able to memorize the short surahs of the al-Qur'an quite well. SA is a grade 3 student at Muhammadiyah 12 Pamulang Elementary School. A quiet student. SA is a student who reads Iqro 5 but SA has been able to memorize short surahs of the al-Qur'an in tahfidz learning. SA has the ability to memorize the al-Qur'an which is quite good. SA is able to memorize short suras by getting good grades. ZW is a grade 3 student at Muhammadiyah 12 Pamulang Elementary School. ZW is a student who is able to read the al-Qur'an. ZW memorized the al-Qur'an well and get good grades.

MA is a grade 3 student at Muhammadiyah 12 Pamulang Elementary School. MA can already read the al-Qur'an. MA is a student who has good memorization skills and gets good tahfidz memorization scores. FN is a 3rd grader at Muhammadiyah 12 Pamulang Elementary School. FN is a student who can read the al-Qur'an. FN can memorize short suras such as al-Bayyinah, al-Qodr, Al-Alaq according to the minimum standard of memorization in grade 3. AA is a grade 3 student at Muhammadiyah 12 Pamulang Elementary School. AA is still reading Iqro but can memorize the short surahs of the al-Qur'an well.

Interpretation of Research Finding

Based on the results of research that have been carried out using data collection techniques, observation, interviews, field notes, and documentation, the interpretation of research results at Muhammadiyah 12 Pamulang Elementary School South Tangerang Indonesia in tahfidz al-Qur'an short surah activities is as follows:

1. How to learn to read the Koran through memorizing short suras. Based on the results of research that has been carried out with several data collection techniques, it can be said that the process of memorizing the al-Qur'an is through memorizing short suras. Learn to read the al-Qur'an through memorizing short chapters of the al-Qur'an at Muhammadiyah 12 Pamulang Elementary School, namely by introducing hijaiyah letters to students using cardboard paper with hijaiyah letters attached and video media, sheets of paper containing the video. Then the teacher teaches students how to pronounce the hijaiyah letters properly and correctly by giving examples of reading according to the makhoriijul letters. Then to memorize the al-Qur'an, grade 3 students are required to memorize short chapters of the al-Qur'an such as Surah Al-Bayyinah, Al-Qodr, Al-Alaq, At-Tiin, Al-Insyirah, Ad-Dhuha, Al-Lail.

2. During the implementation of learning to read the al-Qur'an through memorizing short surahs in class, students are required to repeat the memorization that has been previously memorized together with the goal of memorizing what has been memorized well maintained. Then the teacher reads each verse five to ten times and the students listen to the teacher while looking at Juz 'Amma and the students repeat the verses that have been exemplified by the teacher until they are able to memorize fluently. Each student who has memorized is given the opportunity to come forward to give their memorization and the teacher listens to the memorization that has just been memorized by the students. If there is an error in the student's reading, the teacher corrects it.

3. The method used in learning to read the al-Qur'an. The results of research that have been carried out with several data collection techniques, it can be said that the method used in learning to read the al-Qur'an through memorizing short suras at Muhammadiyah 12 Pamulang Elementary School uses several methods. First is using the takrir method, repeating the memorization, what is meant by takrir is so that the memorization that has been memorized by students is maintained properly. Second, before memorizing the teacher gives an example of reading first and teaches students using the Wahdah method, the child memorizes one verse at a time to be memorized and each verse is read five to ten times to form a pattern in his image. Third, the teacher uses the Sima'I (listening) method by listening to the reading of the verses of the al-Qur'an that will be memorized. So the wahdah and Sima'I methods are combined with the initial stage of the teacher reading each verse five to ten times and students listening to the teacher's reading while looking at Juz'Amma until they can memorize properly and correctly. Fourth is using the talaqqi method, where students give their memorization and the

teacher listens to the memorization that has just been memorized by students and the teacher also checks for mistakes in student memorization.

Supporting and inhibiting factors

Based on the results of research that has been carried out with several data collection techniques, it can be said that learning to read the al-Qur'an through memorizing short suras at Muhammadiyah 12 Pamulang Elementary School has some supporting and inhibiting factors. The first supporting factor is the tahfidz teacher because of his attitude in teaching students to learn to read the al-Qur'an through memorizing short suras patiently and diligently, he teaches his students and always provides support to students who have difficulty reading or memorizing the al-Qur'an. In addition, the second supporting factor from the school is because the school gives motivation and support in educating students to memorize the short surahs of the al-Qur'an by providing opportunities for students to read short suras every morning with loudspeakers. The third factor is from parents, they support their children in terms of murojaah or repeat memorization and track memorization.

Apart from supporting factors, there are inhibiting factors such as when there are children who are sick and cause their memorization to be left behind, children who have difficulty in memorizing because they cannot read the verses of the al-Qur'an, sleepiness, and mood of children affect memorization, and they still want to play. Meanwhile, for the inhibiting factor, the tahfidz teacher does not make it an obstacle and always looks for a solution every time there is an obstacle faced. The obstacles faced by students in memorizing the al-Qur'an are that they find it difficult for children to sign the letters, the suras are long, easy to forget, and lazy.

Conclusion

By the formulation of the problem that has been answered in this study, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Learn to read the Koran through memorizing short suras at Muhammadiyah 12 Pamulang Elementary School by the teacher introducing hijaiyah letters to students using cardboard paper with hijaiyah letters attached and video media, sheets of paper containing the video. Then the teacher teaches students how to pronounce the hijaiyah letters properly and correctly by giving examples of reading according to the makhorijul letters. Then to memorize the al-Qur'an, grade 3 students are required to memorize short chapters of the al-Qur'an such as Surah Al-Bayyinah, Al-Qodr, Al-Alaq, At-Tiin, Al-Insyirah, Ad-Dhuha, Al-Lail. During the implementation of learning to read the al-Qur'an through memorizing short surahs in class, students are required to repeat the memorization that has been previously memorized together with the goal of memorizing what has been memorized well maintained. Then the teacher reads each verse five to ten times and the students listen to the teacher's reading while looking at Juz'Amma and the students repeat the verses that have been exemplified by the teacher until they can memorize fluently. Each student who has memorized is allowed to come forward to deposit his memorization and the teacher listens to the memorization that has just been memorized by the students. If there is an error in the student's reading, the teacher corrects the student's reading. Then the teacher assesses student memorization using a tahfidz book if there are children who have not memorized they are allowed to memorize again.

2. There are several supporting factors in memorizing the al-Qur'an at Muhammadiyah 12 Pamulang Elementary School, South Tangerang City Indonesia namely from the tahfidz teacher himself because of his attitude in teaching students to learn to read the al-Qur'an through memorizing short suras patiently and carefully and good in teaching their students and always provide support to students who have difficulty reading or memorizing short surahs of the al-Qur'an. Then there are internal and external factors, parents. Parents play a role in murojaah or repeating the child's memorization at school and asking where the child's memorization has reached. Parents also play a role in giving gifts so that children are more enthusiastic about memorizing. In addition, the Muhammadiyah Elementary School provides motivation and support for tahfidz al-Qur'an short suras by means that every morning students are given the opportunity for students to read short suras with loudspeakers before entering class by students who have a predetermined schedule and students who read well. The teacher gives a comfortable attitude to students in memorizing short surahs of the Koran so that memorizing is more fun and not made a burden. Then for the inhibiting factor in memorizing the short surahs of the al-Qur'an, it is caused by many things. First, students are sleepy, weak and it affects students' memorization. The two unfinished students became an obstacle because the unfinished students wanted to play with their finished friends so the class atmosphere became crowded and noisy due to students joking and running around. In addition, the inhibiting factors faced by students in memorizing the al-Qur'an are because they find it difficult to mark the letters, the surah is long, lazy, often forget, and find it difficult. tersebut.

Suggestions

A study certainly can not be separated from the advantages and disadvantages. Excess is a positive value of new knowledge. While the lack is motivation that needs improved. With these advantages and disadvantages, it produces a suggestion for the whole community of education observers. The suggestions that can be described by researchers are as follows:

1. To student

Students are the next generation of the nation's youth. A student must start studying the al-Qur'an from an early age or elementary school age to help his development in thinking about studying the al-Qur'an if this activity is carried out continuously it will increase students' knowledge of the al-Qur'an, by memorizing, writing, and listening to the recitation of the Koran. Then for students, it is hoped that they can increase enthusiasm in memorizing short surahs of the al-Qur'an and relearn the virtues and benefits of memorizing the Qur'an. That way the spirit of memorizing the al-Qur'an will be even higher.

2. To Tahfidz teacher

To the tahfidz al-Qur'an teacher to motivate and encourage students to memorize the al-Qur'an through memorizing short surahs so that students can become generations of memorizing the al-Qur'an in the future. Then students are expected to know the virtues and benefits of memorizing the al-Qur'an so that students understand the meaning of memorizing the al-Qur'an.

3. To researcher

Gain hands-on experience in applying the introduction of reading the al-Qur'an through memorizing short surahs to students in elementary schools.

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